

Research Data Management Plan short — DFG Proposal

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No.	Question	Answer
1	General information on research proposal	

1.1	Title of the project (baseline study or further study as part of the baseline study)	The title of the project is:
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1.2	What is the primary research question?	The primary research question is:
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1.3	Which institution or individual is responsible for project management and coordination?	Personal name	Organizational name
		Project manager / sponsor (primary)	
		Name of the affiliation:	
		Address of the affiliation:	
		Webpage of the affiliation:	
		ROR ID of the affiliation:	

1.4	Which project partners are there (institutions / persons)?	Personal name	Organizational name
		Personal name (if applicable)	
		Type of role of partner:	

1.5 Who is responsible for the data curation after the project?

Name of the affiliation:	
Address of the affiliation:	
Webpage of the affiliation:	
ROR ID of the affiliation:	
Personal name	Organizational name:
Data curator	
Name of the affiliation:	
Address of the affiliation:	
Webpage of the affiliation:	
ROR ID of the affiliation:	
	204 Microbiology, Virology und Immunology
	205 Medicine
	206 Neurosciences
Please specify further:	

1.6 Which DFG discipline does this study belong to?

2 Types of data – content

2.1 What data types are generated?

Administrative databases	Biosamples:	Imaging data:
Biological samples	Blood	Computed tomography (CT)
Cognitive measurements	Buccal cells	Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI)
Genealogical records	Cord blood	Radiography (x-ray)
Imaging data	DNA	Ultrasound
Interview	Faeces	Other imaging data
Medical records	Hair	Omics technology:
Omics technology	Immortalized cell lines	Biomarkers
Physiological/Biochemical measurements	Isolated pathogen	Genomics
Questionnaire	Nail	Metabolomics
Registries	Plasma	Proteomics
Other	RNA	Transcriptomics
	Saliva	Other omics technology
	Serum	
	Tissue (FFPE)	
	Tissue (frozen)	
	Urine	
	Other biological samples	

2.2 Are data reused?

Yes

No -> skip question 2.2.a + 2.2.b

2.2.a Which data are reused?

Administrative databases	Biosamples:	Imaging data:
Biological samples	Blood	Computed tomography (CT)
Cognitive measurements	Buccal cells	Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI)
Genealogical records	Cord blood	Radiography (x-ray)
Imaging data	DNA	Ultrasound
Interview	Faeces	Other imaging data
Medical records	Hair	Omics technology:
Omics technology	Immortalized cell lines	Biomarkers
	Isolated pathogen	Genomics
	Nail	Metabolomics

2.2.b Are the re-used data publicly available?

Physiological/Biochemical measurements Questionnaire Registries Other	Plasma RNA Saliva Serum Tissue (FFPE) Tissue (frozen) Urine Other biological samples	Proteomics Transcriptomics Other omics technology
No		
Yes, some of the re-used data are publicly available here:		
Yes, all re-used data are publicly available here:		
DOI:		
URL:		
arXiv:		
EAN13:		
EISSN:		
Handle:		
ISBN:		
ISSN:		
ISTC:		
LISSN:		
LSID:		
PMID:		
PURL:		
URN:		
w3id:		
Other:		

2.3 How does the project generate data?

Here, your methodological approach should be outlined. How do you plan to process (any step applied to produce meaningful information), analyse and -if applicable- present your data?

Data processing: Validation, Sorting, Summarising, Aggregating

Data analysis: Interpretation, Visualisation

3 **Data Formats**

3.1 What is the data volume of all the digital data types to be collected?

Number of KB / MB:

3.2 What measures are taken to ensure data security?

Protection against unauthorized access by:

Transfer of sensitive data is protected by:

Data recovery by means of:

Other:

3.3 Are metadata standards, documentation standards or ontologies used to describe the data?

Metadata standards:

Documentation standards:

Ontologies:

4 **Laws and ethics**

4.1 Does the data set contain sensitive data (BDSG §3, para.9))?

No	
Yes, information on:	
racial and ethnic origin	
political opinions	
religious or philosophical beliefs	
trade union membership	
health	
sex life	
other non-personal sensitive data:	
4.2 Are any access and usage rights in place for sensitive data?	Researchers during project duration:

	Interested parties after the project:	
4.3 Does Copyright / ownership law apply?	The following laws apply:	

5 [Reuse and publication of data](#)

5.1 Where will the metadata and/or study documents be published?	Institutional repository:	
	Specialised repository:	
	Generic repository:	
	Data Journal:	

	Other:	
5.2	Under which terms of use / which licence should the data be published?	Creative Commons 4.0:
	Please specify:	
		Individual data usage contracts
5.3	Which tools/software are required to use/re-use the data?	Tools:
		Software:
6	Storage and long-term archiving	
	Where is the data (including metadata, documentation and any relevant code or software) stored or archived?	The data will be archived in a public repository
		Name of repository
		URL

The data will be archived in a non-public repository (i.e., the data's existence is verifiable, but data is only accessible on request)	
Name of repository	
URL	
The data will be archived in a storage service, integrity and accessibility of the data are guaranteed	
Name of repository	
URL	

Basis: RDMO catalogue of questions (generic catalogue) of 19.11.2019, DFG Handling of research data of 21.12.2021